

"HEALTH CORRIDOR" OF PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT IN CHILDREN FROM 3 TO 7 YEARS OLD LIVING IN THE CITY OF TASHKENT

Mirsharapov Utkur Mirsharapovich
Shermanov Abduvali Ortikovich.

Tashkent Medical Academy, Alfraganus University
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11260533>

Annotation. In our study, we created a "health corridor" with the sentil method based on anthropometric indicators of the physical development of children from 3 to 7 years old in preschool educational institutions living in Tashkent. The value of the observed anthropometric indicators was assessed as a normative indicator if it was in the range of 25-75 sentyls.

The purpose of the study: to create a "health corridor" with the development of centile tables of anthropometric indicators for children from 3 to 7 years old.

Methods of examination: to implement the goal solution set before us, 1329 healthy preschool children were involved in our research and organized by children raised in preschool educational institutions of the city of Tashkent. Of all the children examined, 653 (49.1%) were girls and 676 (50.9%) were boys. Research observations took an average of 1 year. In the study, we used the signal method and evaluated the physical development of children based on the anthropometric data obtained. Sentyll corridors represent this parametric Unbound statistical method. The essence of the Sentyll method is that all the measurement results of a sign or feature are arranged in gradation in the form of a distributed series. It is a distributed series, covering the range of oscillations of an entire character and divided into 100 intervals, with matching a value indicating equal probability. In units of absolute measure, the dimensions of such sentyl intervals will not be the same. The central trend of a correctly distributed series is defined as 50-sentyll (meridian).

Results of the study: from the data obtained, we can say the following. Of the 1,329 children examined, 35 (2.63%) were admitted to very low physical development, 134 (10.1%) to low physical development, 245 (18.4%) to moderately low physical development, 386 (29%) to moderate, 478 (35.9%) to moderately high physical development, 32 (2.4%) to high physical development, and 19 (1.44%) to very high physical development. 280 children were found to deviate from the norms of the accepted anthropometric indicators. The physical development of these children does not meet the average standards for this age.

Conclusion. The results of the study showed that 29% of children examined were included in the 4 corridor of the "health corridor", 35.9% in the 5 corridor, and, on average, in the category of physical development and above. 1-,2-,6-,7-children who are included in the corridor are definitely recommended to be examined by deep specialists. Children are in constant growth and Development, their future largely depends on how the child grows and develops, and therefore this process should be under the constant supervision of parents, doctors and teachers from the moment the child was born to the period of maturity. The normal course of growth and development of a child ensures a comfortable state of his body, indicates the absence of harmful effects, and physical development at this age is one of the leading signs of Health, which depends on his other indicators.

Bibliography:

1. Anguera, M. T. (2001). Cómo apresar las competencias del bebé mediante una aplicación de la metodología observacional [How to capture the baby's skills through an application of observational methodology]. *Contextos Educativos* 4, 13–34. doi: 10.18172/con.484
2. Minullina A. F. Short lecture notes on the discipline "Age-related anatomy, physiology and hygiene" in the field of special training (defectological education) in the profile "speech therapy", "special psychology", "preschool defectology" 1st year, 1 semester. Moscow: 2014, - 69 p.
3. Paranichevat.M. The role of morphophysiological and psychophysiological features of first-graders in adapting to the educational load / T.M. Paranicheva // Education and upbringing of children and adolescents: hygienic problems: Mat. I Congress of the Russian Society of School and University Medicine and Health - M.: NO NTSD RAMS, 2008. - pp. 213-215
4. Paranicheva T.M., Tyurina E.V. Health and physical development dynamics of the health status of preschool and primary school age children. // *New research.* – 2012. – № 4 (33) – P.68.
5. Stepanenkova E.Ya. Theory and methodology of physical education and development. — M.: Publishing center "Academy", 2006. — 368 p.
6. Tarasova T.A. "Control of the physical condition of preschool children". Methodological recommendations for managers and teachers of the Preschool Educational institution.– M., 2005. – 176 p.
7. Physical development of children and adolescents at the turn of the millennium / Baranov A.A., Kuchma V.R., Skoblina N.A. – M.: Publisher Scientific Center for Children's Health of the Russian Academy of Medical Sciences. 2008. – 216 p.: ill.

8. Kholodov Zh.K., Kuznetsov B.C. Theory and methodology of physical education and sports: Textbook for students. higher. studies. institutions. - M.: Publishing center "Academy", 2000. - 480 p.
9. Shcheplyagina L.A. Physiology of growth and development of children and adolescents. In 2 volumes. M.: GEOTAR - Media., 2006 — 896c.

